

CERAMICS IN EUROPE

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Glass-ceramics from glass powders and reactive silicone binders: from sealants to additive manufacturing

Hamada Elsayed¹, Matías Stabile², Paulina Ožóg³, Jozef Kraxner⁴, Dusan Galusek⁴, Enrico Bernardo¹

¹ Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Padova, Padova, Italy

² Department of Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, National University of La Plata (UNLP), La Plata, Argentina

³ FunGlass–Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubcek University of Trenčín, Trenčín, Slovakia

⁴ Centre for functional and surface-functionalized glass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Trenčín, Slovakia

Abstract:

A target glass-ceramic system may be processed by means of a novel technique, relying on the reaction of glass powders with silicone polymers. Instead of the parent glass, a 'silica-defective variant' is considered. A fundamental feature is the fact that the silicone polymer act as binders for glass powders from room temperature up to the firing temperature, at which, operating in air, they convert into silica. The interaction between 'silica-defective' glass powders and binder-derived silica allows for the recovery of the original stoichiometry. The overall process has important advantages when glass powders lead to glass-ceramics, by sinter-crystallization, after the burn-out of organic binders. The shape of components may be lost simply by sliding of particles before the activation of viscous flow. Silicones, besides providing an extended binding action up to the maximum firing temperature, stabilize the shapes during sintering. Otherwise, a significant viscous flow of softened glass is prevented by the formation of a rigid silica skeleton, from the transformation of the silicone binder. After successful preliminary applications to glass-ceramic sealants for SOFC, we will present an extension to glass-ceramic scaffolds, for tissue engineering applications, manufactured by the application of advanced additive manufacturing technologies. We will show that reactions in nitrogen enable the transformation of silicone binders into silica and pyrolytic carbon, in turn leading, by reaction with glass powders, to novel glass-ceramic/C composites.

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